

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

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Lead beneficiary:	NRI
Author:	Maruthi M N Gowda m.n.maruthi@gre.ac.uk
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D4.4 Meta study on the evolution of viruses to cause disease epidemics (M54, R, PU).

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AC4 - AC4 protein

CP – Coat protein

IR - intergenic region

NRI – Natural Resources Institute

Pre-CP - Pre-coat protein

REn - Replication enhancer protein

Rep - Replication protein

ToLCKV-T – Tomato leaf curl Karnataka virus-T (tomato-specific)

ToLCNDV-C – Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus-Cucurbit strain (cucurbit-specific)

ToLCNDV-CB - Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus-CB strain (cucurbit-specific)

ToLCNDV-TC – Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus-Tomato and cucurbit strain (tomato and cucurbit-specific)

TrAp - transcriptional activator protein

WU – Wageningen University

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

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Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV) was reported for the first time from India in 1995. Since then, the virus has spread to at least a dozen Asian countries. In 2014, the virus was also inadvertently introduced into Spain and currently causing a major epidemic of leaf curl disease of cucurbit crops in at least 10 European countries. As the name suggests, the virus was originally described to infect tomatoes but was subsequently found to infect more than 100 plant species including wild plants and some economically important crops like potatoes, peppers, papaya, cucurbits, ladies' finger, cotton, beans, and several pulse crops. While the virus is spreading geographically and also expanding in its host range, the mechanism of this spread is not known. In this deliverable D4.4, we investigated the role of both viral and host factors contributing to this rapid and aggressive spread to ToLCNDV. We believe that if uncontrolled, ToLCNDV will spread to all parts of warm climatic regions and into the protected environments of colder climates of the world.

Our research involved two major lines of work, investigating the role of both **viral** and **host factors** in expanding the host range of ToLCNDV and thus their evolution. For investigating the role of viral factors, Natural Resources Institute (NRI) developed infectious clones of three host-specific viruses: ToLCNDV-C (cucurbit-specific virus, can infect only cucurbits), ToLCNDV-TC (tomato- and cucurbit-specific virus, can infect both tomato and cucurbits), and Tomato leaf curl Karnataka virus-T (ToLCKV-T) - can infect only tomatoes. All three viruses, however, infected the experimental host plant *Nicotiana benthamiana* which serves as a positive control. Results of many NRI studies involving chimeric viruses and co-inoculating with non-cognate DNA molecules showed that only TrAp and REn proteins caused the virus switch between tomato and cucurbit plants. In addition, Wageningen University (WU) did similar research but with a different set of ToLCNDV strains: ToLCNDV-CB (cucurbit-specific) and ToLCNDV-TC (both tomato and cucurbit). They produced contrasting results in that the -TC DNA-B made the -CB strain to switch from cucurbits to tomato, clearly indicating the role of DNA-B in host specificity.

In another set of experiments, we investigated the host proteins interacting with the begomoviruses and there also found some novel interactions. For example, polyA, protein of tomato interacted with REn of all three viruses and this was expected because polyA is involved in DNA synthesis. In contrast, the RBR proteins did not interact, which was not expected because RBR is the site of synthesis of viral DNAs. Similarly, ATG-7 and rgsCam proteins of tomato also interacted with both tomato and cucurbit viruses, which were also unexpected because we were not expecting the tomato proteins to interact with cucurbit-specific viruses. Nevertheless, these results indicate hitherto unexplained complex plant-viral protein interactions that require more in depth molecular studies to understand the underlying interactions, which influence virus adaptation and evolution.

2 INTRODUCTION – INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF VIRAL FACTORS IN HOST JUMP

2.1 Infectious clones and chimeric viruses

At NRI, we first created infectious clones of the three viruses, which was followed by creating a series of chimeric viruses and mixing non-cognate DNA components for testing the role of various viral proteins on host switch. The following combinations were investigated.

- 1) **Experiment 1:** The reciprocal combination of ToLCNDV-C DNA-A + ToLCNDV-TC DNA-B and ToLCNDV-TC DNA-A + ToLCNDV-C DNA-B.
Results: None of the combinations produced infection in any crop species including *N. benthamiana*.
Conclusions: Combinations of the genome components from the two ToLCNDV strains tested are incompatible and fail to initiate infection in any of the original host plants. So, our attention turned to viral genes and other virus combinations.
- 2) **Experiment 2:** ToLCKV-T DNA-A + ToLCNDV-C DNA-B; and ToLCKV-T DNA-A + ToLCNDV-TC DNA-B.
Results: Only the ToLCKV-T + ToLCNDV-TC DNA-B combination resulted in virus replication in *N. benthamiana* and tomatoes. No infection was found on cucurbits.
Conclusions: The multiplication of non-cognate viral DNA molecules (recognized by the intergenic IR region) is a lot more complex than observed in experiment 1 above. So, it is possible that DNA-B can play a role in host-switch between tomato and cucurbits in some viruses. This is a very specific virus-virus interaction, rather than a universal mechanism.
- 3) **Experiment 3:** Swapping the replication (Rep) and AC4 proteins between all three viruses (Figure 1)
Results: None of the chimeric viruses were infectious in any host.
Conclusions: Rep and AC4 are not contributing to host-switch between tomato and cucurbits.
- 4) **Experiment 4:** Swapping the Pre-CP and coat proteins (CP) between all three viruses (Figure 1)
Results: None of the chimeric viruses were infectious in any host.
Conclusions: Pre-CP and CP did not contribute to host-switch between tomato and cucurbits.
- 5) **Experiment 5:** Swapping the transcriptional activator (TrAp) and replication enhancer (Ren) proteins between all three viruses (Figures 1 and 2).
Results: a) Swapping of TrAp and REn caused the cucurbit strain (C) to infect tomato, and the tomato strain (T) to infect cucurbit for the first time in our experimental conditions.
b) Providing a cucurbit TrAp/ REn to the tomato strain (TC) abolished infection of tomatoes.
Conclusions: Unequivocal evidence was obtained on the role of TrAp and REn in host-switch between tomato and cucurbit species by the ToLCNDVs and ToLCKV.

2.2 Role of non-cognate DNA molecules

At WU, similar mix-genome experiments were conducted but with a different ToLCNDV strain. The non-cognate DNA molecules of ToLCNDV-CB (cucurbit-specific) and ToLCNDV-TC (infecting both tomato and cucurbit) were mixed and inoculated into tomato plants. The ToLCNDV-CB DNA-A + ToLCNDV-TC DNA-B combination resulted in systemic infection of tomato plants, showing even more severe symptoms and viral accumulation than the wild-type ToLCNDV-TC DNA-A+B. (Figure 3). This provided evidence for the role of DNA-B in host switching but also an indication that the DNA-A component influences the level of virulence.

Figure 3. Infectivity of mix-genome components between the ToLCNDV-TC and -CB in tomatoes.

2.3 Host protein interactions

At NRI, we screened TrAp against known plant proteins such as AGO, rgsCam and ATG7, while REn was screened with PCNa, PolyA and RBR proteins. While some proteins interacted as expected—for example, tomato polyA-binding protein interacted with REn (AC3) from all viruses—others, such as the RBR protein, did not interact with any REn (AC3s). Some unique and unexpected interactions were seen for AGO1 and PCNa (Figure 4). For example, the TrAp (AC2) of cucurbit virus interacted with tomato AGO1 but not with the expected cucumber AGO1. Similar results were obtained for TrAp with PCNa where only some viruses interacted but not all. These results are indicating the deep complex virus and plant-specific interactions, which will require further investigations.

Figure 4. Yeast two-hybrid analysis shows varied and novel interactions between TrAp, REn, and selected plant proteins.

2.3.1 Conclusions

At NRI, the DNA-A–encoded proteins TrAp and REn were clearly shown to contribute to host switching between tomato and cucurbits in three highly host-specific viruses: ToLCNDV-C, ToLCNDV-TC, and ToLCKV-T. Moreover, NRI demonstrated that ToLCKV-T was able to amplify the non-cognate ToLCNDV-TC DNA-B, indicating the involvement of DNA-B in host switching in these viruses. At WU, it was shown that DNA-B is the key component responsible for host-range specificity between ToLCNDV-TC and a different strain restricted to cucurbits, ToLCNDV-CB.

These results suggest that host-range specificity is not determined by a single viral factor but instead arises from the interplay of multiple viral components, making the outcome strain- or virus-specific. The present studies provide novel insights into the mechanisms that determine host-range specificity in these viruses.

Building on our results and further expanding this knowledge by identifying host-range determinants in additional viral strains and related viruses will help elucidate the complex mechanisms controlling this process. Such knowledge will support the development of diagnostic markers, improve our understanding of the host factors involved, and potentially reveal host targets useful for resistance breeding. Altogether, these advances can contribute to more efficient and sustainable strategies to mitigate the impact of these viruses in agriculture and to prevent future epidemics.